

**THE NONLINEAR VISCOELASTIC BEHAVIOUR OF A RANDOMLY ORIENTATED
FIBRE REINFORCED POLYMER UNDER ABRUPT CHANGES IN APPLIED STRESS**

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ABSTRACT

The time-dependent response of a randomly orientated chopped glass fibre reinforced polyester laminate to uniaxial tensile stepped-stress histories is investigated. A nonlinear viscoelastic material model developed using Schapery's single integral constitutive equation and single step creep and creep recovery data is used to predict material response. The experimental behaviour of the composite is examined at stress levels both above and below the transition between the two distinct modes of nonlinear stress-dependence displayed by the creep recovery data.

INTRODUCTION

It is well known that polymers behave in a viscoelastic manner and that composites fabricated from elastic fibres and polymeric matrices are therefore viscoelastic. Glass fibre reinforced polyester (g.r.p) composite materials have been used for many years in the construction industry. However, the design of engineering components is restricted by the lack of understanding of many aspects of the time-dependent material response.

Long-term material property data may be obtained from a simple uniaxial constant stress creep testing programme. However, it is necessary to develop viscoelastic theory to predict, from creep compliance data, the

behaviour of materials when under non-constant loading regimes. Linear viscoelastic principles have been widely used in the characterisation of the mechanical behaviour of polymers [1]. However, the concept of linearity is only applicable at low applied stress. At high levels of stress the behaviour of polymers can become highly nonlinear and the applicability of linear principles is questionable [2]. This is also true for many composite materials with polymer matrices. Here the problem is compounded by the complex micro-structure and relative stiffnesses of the constituent materials which can cause high stress concentrations even when the material is lightly loaded. These phenomena can cause nonlinear material response over a wide range of applied stress [3].

Theories developed to model observed nonlinear viscoelastic behaviour range from early adaptations on the linear integral of Boltzmann, such as the 'Modified Superposition Principle' (M.S.P) of Leaderman [4], and Findley et. al. [5,6], to multiple integral representations, such as that of Green and Rivlin [7,8]. The former has limited application, nonlinearity being modelled in a single function of stress. The latter equation is sufficiently general to be used to model completely every aspect of the time- and stress-dependent behaviour. However, the determination of the material functions would necessitate undertaking a prohibitive number of experiments even if the integral series were truncated after the third term [9].

Schapery [10] developed a constitutive equation based on thermodynamic theory which retains the simplicity of the single integral relation but with the capability of modelling complex nonlinear stress dependence. Schapery's theory was used to determine the nonlinear viscoelastic characteristics of the material under investigation [11], and is extended here to evaluate the response of the composite to stepped-stress histories.

MATERIAL MODEL

Single step creep and creep recovery data were used in conjunction with the nonlinear viscoelastic single integral equation of Schapery to characterise the material response. The details of the procedure used are given in [11].

Schapery's equation for an isotropic material under uniaxial loading and subject to isothermal conditions can be written:

$$\varepsilon(t) = g_0 \cdot D_0 \cdot \sigma + g_1 \cdot \int_0^t D_1(\psi - \psi') \cdot \frac{dg_2 \sigma}{d\tau} \cdot d\tau \quad \text{----- (1)}$$

where D_0 is the initial, time-independent, component of the compliance and $D_1(\psi)$ is the transient, time-dependent, component of the compliance. The reduced time parameter, ψ , is defined as:

$$\psi = \int_0^t \frac{dt'}{a_\sigma} \quad \text{and} \quad \psi' = \int_0^\tau \frac{d\tau'}{a_\sigma} \quad \text{----- (2)}$$

It is of interest to note that when the stress-dependent function $g_0 = g_1 = g_2 = a_\sigma = 1$, equation (1) reduces to the Boltzmann Superposition Integral which describes linear viscoelastic behaviour. Also when $g_0 = g_1 = a_\sigma = 1$ nonlinearity is modelled entirely by g_2 which renders the equation to that of Leaderman's M.S.P.

It has been determined [11] that, for the material tested, below a stress threshold of 23 N/mm^2 , the material can be modelled adequately by the simpler M.S.P, where the function g_2 is the only non unity stress operator. However, beyond this threshold the stress-reduced time parameter a_σ deviates from unity, resulting in a less simple relation. It was also noted that the nonlinear stress dependence of the creep compliance was modelled, over the entire stress range considered, by a hyperbolic sine function. A summary of the stress operator relations can be seen in fig 1.

The material model, given in equation (1), can now be simplified to facilitate the prediction of the model response to a complex stepped stress history.

Figure 1. Nonlinear stress operators.

The equation can be reduced to that for a series of discrete stepped stress inputs:

$$\epsilon(t) = D_0 \cdot \sigma_m + \sum_{n=1}^m \{ (g_2^n \cdot \sigma_n - g_2^{n-1} \cdot \sigma_{n-1}) \cdot D_1(t) \} \quad \text{----- (3)}$$

where:

$$D_1(t) = \left[\sum_{i=n}^{m-1} (t_i - t_{i-1}) / a_\sigma^i \right] + (t - t_{m-1}) / a_\sigma^m \quad \text{----- (4)}$$

and: t = time of observation ($t > t_m$)

σ_n = stress applied at time, t_n

$g_2^n = g_2(\sigma_n)$

$a_\sigma^n = a_\sigma(\sigma_n)$

m = total number of steps occurring before time of observation.

The creep compliance transient component, D_1 , was found to be of the form of a power law relation [11]:

$$D_1 = A \cdot t^n \quad \text{----- (5)}$$

where A and n are material constants and therefore the basic creep equation can be expressed in the form:

$$\epsilon_c(t) = g_2 \cdot A \cdot (t/a_\sigma)^n \cdot \sigma \quad \text{----- (6)}$$

The solution of equation (3), using a small time step, will give the numerical solution to the nonlinear viscoelastic problem. This procedure has been used to evaluate the applicability of the material model under three step stress histories where the stress-step magnitudes are both above and below the nonlinear mode transition threshold.

STEPPED-STRESS TESTING

The evaluation of the material model has been achieved through the experimental determination of the time-dependent strain response of test coupons to stepped-stress histories.

The material used in the study was a pseudo-isotropic composite which was fabricated from chopped strand glass fibre mat (randomly orientated short fibre) and a polyester resin (Scott Bader's Crystic 1355Pa), a typical g.r.p system which is used in the construction industry. The test coupons were cut from panels fabricated for the initial characterisation tests.

When undertaking the measurement of small changes in strain, over relatively long periods of time it is essential to use a measurement system which is both sufficiently sensitive and yet highly stable. The extensometry used for measurement in this investigation has been developed from a system of displacement control, used for many years by mechanical engineers, which is based on pneumatic principles. The extensometer system has proved to be highly stable over test durations of 500 hours and has a sensitivity which is dependent on the range of displacement required.

A strain resolution of 5×10^{-6} over a calibrated range of 8×10^{-4} was found to be suitable for the material and the test coupon geometry used. It was necessary, due to the nonlinearity of the calibration data, to use a micro-computer for data reduction during testing.

The creep test facility, utilised for the long-term stepped loading of the material, has a lever loading system with a ratio of 1:10 giving a maximum working load capacity of 10kn at each of the twenty testing stations. Applied loading is monitored via a load cell which is mounted in series with the test coupon and is trapped beneath the lower member of the testing rig. The whole test facility is housed within a temperature controlled environment. The test temperature was held at a constant 25°C throughout the duration of the investigation.

Details of the testing arrangement in general, the pneumatic strain measuring system and the static short- and long-term loading characteristics of the material can be found in [11].

Spec.	Load-Step 1		Load-Step 2		Load-Step 3	
	σ_1 (N/mm^2)	t_1 (hours)	σ_2 (N/mm^2)	t_2 (hours)	σ_3 (N/mm^2)	t_3 (hours)
TC2S1	6.88	70	29.50	188	0	400
TC2S2	24.60	70	13.75	190	0	400
TC2S3	36.87	72	26.56	192	0	400
TC3S1	6.24	70	23.90	188	0	400
TC3S2	19.60	70	13.80	190	0	400
TC3S3	40.29	70	22.04	190	0	400
TC4S1	6.97	70	17.97	188	0	400
TC4S2	38.76	70	15.71	190	0	400

Table 1. Summary of test parameters.

The testing procedure used for each coupon was essentially identical. At the start of each test, time $t = 0$, the first loading increment was applied to the test piece, the load monitored and recorded and the magnitude of the strain monitored and recorded over the load-step duration, generally up to time $t_1 = 70$ hours. The period between strain measurement ranged from 5 minutes at the start of the load-step to 10 hours after 20 hours of loading. The procedure for the first load-step was repeated for subsequent steps. The timing of each of the load-steps was kept constant but the sign and magnitude of step varied for each test. A summary of testing parameters is given in Table 1 and a generalised loading history is shown in fig 2.

Figure 2. Generalised loading history.

RESULTS

The material model has been used to evaluate the time-dependent behaviour of the composite material tested. Typical creep strain data compared with the model response can be seen in figs 3 to 6.

The theoretical model was developed using a single integral viscoelastic constitutive equation together with single step creep and creep recovery test data to define the material constants and stress functions. Two distinct modes of nonlinear stress-dependence were noted using this procedure. At stress levels below 23 N/mm^2 the nonlinearity can be

Figure 3. Creep strain response (TC3S2).

Figure 4. Creep strain response (TC3S1).

Figure 5. Creep strain response (TC2S1).

Figure 6. Creep strain response (TC4S2).

adequately modelled by a single hyperbolic sine stress function, g_2 . Above this threshold the stress-dependence becomes more complex and is modelled using two nonlinear functions, a_σ and g_2 . The inter-relation of the nonlinear stress parameters can be seen in fig 1.

The stepped-tests were conducted at levels of stress both above and below the observed nonlinear stress mode transition. The behaviour when all steps are below the transition stress level is modelled by the M.S.P, as described previously. Examination of the data obtained for this case reveals relatively good agreement between the material model and the experimental time-dependent response of the composite both when the second step is deductive, fig 3, and additive, fig 4. In all cases there is no evidence of any delayed recovery mechanism.

The behaviour after stress-steps greater than that of the transition level is modelled by equations containing the additional stress-reduced time parameter. Typical data for these cases can be seen in figs 5 and 6. The behaviour of the material model is presented for the case of the M.S.P and that of the full relation, equation (4). Examination of the time-dependent response of the composite compared to that of the two theoretical relations indicates that some disagreement has occurred. The time-dependent strain response in all those cases following deductive stress-steps can be seen to display recovery at a greater rate than predicted by the model, but at a slower rate than would be expected if no stress-induced delayed recovery mechanism existed. For the case of an additive second stress increment good agreement of data occurs. This result is expected, since the two equations are identical during the second phase, because stress-induced delayed recovery only takes place as a result of a change in stress above the transition point.

OBSERVATIONS

It is apparent that, for the stepped-stress histories examined, the material model is adequate for cases below the nonlinear stress operator transition threshold. However, the model which was generated using creep recovery data beyond the applicable range of the single nonlinear stress function does not give good agreement with the results obtained.

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REFERENCES

1. Ferry, J. D., *Viscoelastic Properties of Polymers*, John Wiley and Sons, 3rd Ed., New York, 1980.
2. Lockett, F. J., Assessment of the Linearity and Characterisation of Nonlinear Behaviour, in *Mech. of Viscoelastic Media and Bodies*, IUTAM Symp., Gottenburg, 1974.
3. Lou, Y. C. and Schapery, R. A., Viscoelastic Characterisation of a Nonlinear Fibre-Reinforced Plastic, *J. Comp. Mats.*, V5, p208, 1971.
4. Leaderman, H., *Elastic and Creep Properties of Filamentous Materials and Other High Polymers*, Textile Foundation, Washington D.C., 1943.
5. Findley, W. N. and Khosla, G., Application of the Superposition Principle and Theories of Mechanical Equation of State, Strain and Time Hardening to Creep of Plastics under Changing Loads, *J. Appl. Phys.*, V26, 7, pp821-832, 1955.
6. Findley, W. N. and Lai, J. S. Y., A Modified Superposition Principle Applied to Creep of Nonlinear Viscoelastic Material under Abrupt Changes in State of Combined Stress, *Trans. Soc. Rheol.* VII, 3, pp361-380, 1967.
7. Green, A. E. and Rivlin, R. S., *The Mechanics of Nonlinear Materials with Memory*, Part I, *Arch. Rat. Mech. Anal.*, VI, 1957.
8. Green, A. E., Rivlin, R. S. and Spencer, A. J. M., *The Mechanics of Nonlinear Materials with Memory*, Part II, *Arch. Rat. Mech. Anal.*, VI, 1959.
9. Lockett, F. J., *Nonlinear Viscoelastic Solids*, Academic Press, 1972.
10. Schapery, R. A., On the Characterisation of Nonlinear Viscoelastic Materials, *Polym. Eng. Sci.*, V9, 4, pp295-310, 1969.
11. Howard, C. M. and Hollaway, L., The Characterisation of the Non-linear Viscoelastic Properties of a Randomly Orientated Fibre/Matrix Composite, to be published in "J. of Composites", September 1987.